

Original Research

Evaluation of the Degree of Non-Linear Exchange Rate Pass-Through in Different Consumption Groups in Iran

Mahdi Aminirad¹

Department of Economics, The Institute for Management and Planning Studies (IMPS), Tehran, Iran

Sima Shaygan Mehr

Department of Economics, Shiraz University, Shiraz, Iran

Received 19 August 2024 Revised 29 October 2024 Accepted 3 November 2024

Abstract

The effect of exchange rate changes on prices is one of the controversial economic issues that has attracted the attention of policymakers and academics. Knowing about the exchange rate Pass-through (ERPT) and its reaction to different inflation environments helps economic policy makers to adopt appropriate exchange policies. In this paper, the effect of exchange rate changes on consumer price index groups (CPI & 12 COICOP categories) has been analyzed using the threshold vector autoregression (TAR) model in Iran. For this purpose, quarterly data for the period 2000Q2-2023Q3 have been used. In this research, the inflation rate of the previous quarter is considered a threshold variable, and two inflation regimes (high and low) are determined based on it. According to the results, although the ERPT for CPI is larger in the high inflation regime than in the low inflation regime in Iran; however, significant differences can be seen between the two inflation regimes in the 12 COICOP categories. In the low inflation regime, the ERPT among COICOP categories varies between 0.138 to 0.783. In the high inflation regime, the ERPT among COICOP categories varies between 0.217 and 0.854.

Keywords: COICOP, ERPT, Inflation expectations, TAR.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: m.aminirad@imps.ac.ir

Introduction

The effect of exchange rate changes on inflation, which is known in international economic literature as exchange rate Pass-through (ERPT), is known as one of the important causes of inflationary pressures in open economies. The exchange rate plays a dual role in the macroeconomic adjustment process. On the one hand, the exchange rate is at the core of the monetary policy transmission mechanism, and on the other hand, changes in the exchange rate help to accommodate shocks (both foreign & domestic) through changes in the real exchange rate. These two roles are key in open economies with inflation-targeting regimes. For the exchange rate to be able to play these two roles effectively, the exchange rate Pass-through must be different for types of goods & services and be significantly higher for tradable goods than for non-tradable goods. If the ERPT is the same for both categories of goods, changes in the nominal exchange rate will not lead to an adjustment in the real exchange rate, and the economy will face a more costly external adjustment process (Edwards & Cabezas, 2022). Keeping inflation at low and stable levels is a challenge in most developing countries, especially open economies. The degree of adaptation of domestic prices to exchange rate changes is Meaningful in understanding inflation dynamics in these economies. In particular, the exchange rate provides a substantial transmission channel for monetary policy to the standard aggregate demand channel (Frimpong & Adam, 2010). Numerous empirical studies have estimated the sensitivity of domestic prices to exchange rate fluctuations, based on which it has been confirmed that the ERPT has decreased significantly in countries over the past few decades. The reduction of ERPT in these studies is mainly related to changing the composition of imported goods (Campa & Goldberg, 2005), increased price stability (Choudhri & Hakura, 2006), and increased credibility of monetary policy (Carrière-Swallow, Firat, Furceri, & Jiménez, 2023).

Developing countries heavily rely on foreign currency for international trade, causing their ERPT elasticity to vary depending on the economic sector composition and exposure to global economic and financial changes (Beirne, Renzhi, & Panthi, 2024). Given the increasing global financial integration, emerging market economies are at risk of global financial shocks and monetary spillovers, particularly through the exchange rate channel (Han & Wei, 2018).

To estimate the ERPT, we must determine how the central bank reacts to exchange rate changes. In particular, monetary authorities may look beyond exchange rate changes to price levels, but respond to exchange rate changes if the effect of the exchange rate on inflation is persistent. The risk of wrong actions in policy is higher if the exchange rate impact on inflation is not properly assessed, especially in emerging markets and developing economies; Because in these countries, exchange rate changes are more severe and central banks are more willing to respond to it (Calvo & Reinhart, 2002).

Iran has experienced several currency shocks in recent years. The average price of the dollar in the market in terms of Rials in the first quarter of 2000 was about 8013 Rials. This index had a relatively slow growth until 2010q1 so that in the 2010q1, it increased by about 44% compared to 2000q1. However, from the middle of 2010 onwards and with the increase of international sanctions, the growth of the dollar price in the Iranian market

intensified, so that in 2011Q4, the average price of the dollar in terms of Rials in the Iranian market increased to 35,017 Rials. Until the end of 2016, the growth of the dollar price in the Iranian market was relatively small and negative in some periods. However, with Trump's withdrawal from the JCPOA and the tightening of sanctions, the price of the dollar in Iran's market experienced a new record, so that the average price of the dollar exceeded 248 thousand rials in the 2020q4. In the years 2021 and 2022, when Iran witnessed strong and various Civil protests, the price of the dollar experienced a sharp increase, and in the 2022q4, the average price of the dollar increased to more than 455 thousand rials. The question raised here is whether the effect of the exchange rate on different groups of the consumer price index is different. If the answer is positive, which consumer groups are less and which are more affected by the exchange rate, and what is the degree of ERPT between consumption categories?

In this paper, the consumer price index data in the Iranian economy is used to analyze the degree of ERPT. In particular, we examine how changes in market exchange rates are transmitted to different consumer price index groups (COICOP). Specifically, in this research, the groups of consumer goods and services are ranked from the highest to the lowest based on the size of the ERPT. In addition, we will investigate whether ERPT changes significantly across consumption groups and inflation regimes. We specifically examine the years 2000 to 2023 because during this period the exchange rate in Iran has experienced more severe changes.

Theoretical framework

Channels of influence of exchange rate on inflation rate

The theoretical foundation of ERPT relies on models such as the Mundell-Fleming, which indicates that a depreciation in the exchange rate results in higher import prices and, consequently, domestic inflation. The incomplete ERPT model suggests that not all changes in exchange rates lead to proportional adjustments in prices. The degree of ERPT depends on various factors, including market structure, pricing behavior, and the types of imported goods. Additionally, New Keynesian models emphasize the importance of nominal rigidities and imperfect competition in influencing the extent of ERPT (Srithilat, Samatmanivong, Sisouphanthong, & Vanhnalat, 2024).

Goldberg & Knetter (1997) have shown incomplete ERPT using the two concepts of import price elasticity relative to exchange rate and exchange rate pass-through to import price index. They called the percentage change in the import price a result of a one percent change in the exchange rate between the exporting and importing countries' ERPT. According to Goldberg & Knetter (1997), if the rate of change in the exchange rate is transferred one-to-one to the import price, the ERPT will be complete, and if it is less than one, the ERPT will be incomplete. The concept of ERPT is closely related to the price of goods and services. After economists studied the macro-effects of the response of exported and imported goods to exchange rate fluctuations, they proposed this concept (Goldberg & Knetter, 1997).

The relationship between prices and exchange rates is based on the concept of purchasing power parity (PPP), which is derived from the law of one price. The

underlying assumption is that there are no trade barriers or transport costs. However, in real-world situations, trade frictions exist, which distort the assumptions of PPP. The law of one price says that in the absence of trade frictions, and under a system of free competition and price flexibility, identical goods sold in different locations must be sold for the same price when prices are expressed in the same currency. This means that changes in the domestic currency in a market would result in an equal change in price in the foreign market, even if the markets are in two different countries. However, because of trade frictions, the law of one price may not hold in certain instances. This is due to factors such as the cost of production, producers' mark-up, and movements in exchange rates, all of which can influence domestic and import prices (Jakpa, Ezi, & Egbon, 2024).

The exchange rate indirectly impacts consumer inflation through net imports and exports, the balance of payments, and the prices of imported goods. When the foreign currency appreciates against the domestic currency, the value of exports increases while the cost of imports decreases. This situation can lead to a rise in net exports (NX) and an improvement in the trade balance. As a result of increased exports, the IS curve shifts to the right in the IS-LM model, leading to higher domestic interest rates. In the short term, an inflow of foreign currency into the domestic market can improve the balance of payments. Two possibilities may arise in this scenario. Firstly, the central bank may need to inject additional domestic currency to stabilize the exchange rate, which could lead to increased inflation due to the expansion of the money supply. Secondly, if the central bank's objective is not to stabilize the domestic currency, the currency supply in the economy will continue to rise. For economies highly reliant on exchange rates, this continuous increase in the total money supply can exert pressure on prices and lead to increased inflation. Furthermore, changes in the exchange rate can also contribute to inflation by raising production costs. Imported goods may serve as inputs for domestic production or as consumer goods. If imported inputs are used in domestic production, an increase in the exchange rate may shift the aggregate supply (AS) curve to the left, leading to higher input prices and inflationary pressures. Additionally, an increase in the exchange rate can raise the prices of imported consumer goods, further contributing to inflationary pressures (Hoang, Thi, & Minh, 2020).

According to the studies of (Goldfajn & Werlang, 2000), (Taylor, 2000) & (Campa & Goldberg, 2005), as leading researchers in the field of exchange rate pass-through, it can be argued that the amount of ERPT depends on Variables such as the degree of openness of the economy, production gap, inflation environment, and exchange rate deviations.

High inflation environments can lead to an increase in ERPT (Taylor, 2000). When the countries are in high inflation situations, the impact of exchange rate changes on the price level increases and, in these conditions, the degree of ERPT will be completely different from the low inflation conditions. High inflation conditions can increase the impact of exchange rate on the price of imported goods through the increase of production costs. The dependence of ERPT on inflation regimes shows that the reaction of economic agents to exchange rate fluctuations will be different in different inflation rates (Mirdala, 2014). Based on theoretical and empirical evidence, the level of economic openness has a positive correlation with the degree of ERPT (McCarthy, 2007). The higher the degree of openness, the lower the ERPT. In the exchange rate system, whether it is a floating exchange rate system or a fixed exchange rate system, producers are less inclined to

exchange rate fluctuations. Therefore, with the increase of exchange rate fluctuations, the ERPT shows a downward trend. Monetary policy also affects the amount of ERPT. In a low inflation environment, the ERPT will be relatively limited (Taylor, 2000). In a high-inflation environment, the level of ERPT flexibility is usually relatively high. The ERPT is also generally in sync with an economic cycle. When an economy enters a recession, firms reduce their profits instead of increasing ERPT (Goldfajn & Werlang, 2000). When exchange rate volatility increases, exporters are more likely to ERPT fluctuations to exported goods. Therefore, there is a positive relationship between exchange rate volatility and ERPT effect. Through empirical research, Frankel concluded that GNP is also one of the factors affecting the ERPT and that there is a negative relationship between the two (Frankel, Parsley, & Wei, 2011).

Figure 1. Pass-through from an exchange rate depreciation to consumer prices
 Source: (Lafliche, 1996)

According to Figure (1), exchange rate changes directly affect the prices of imported goods. However, increased costs for manufacturers and retailers resulting from a devaluation of the national currency are rarely fully or directly reflected in consumer prices. The size and speed of ERPT depend on various factors, including the demand conditions, the cost of price adjustment, and the continued devaluation of the national currency. A decrease in the value of the national currency will cause a change in the composition of demand and an increase in domestic demand and foreign demand for domestic goods. Higher prices for imported goods will lead to increased demand for domestic substitute goods and upward pressure on the prices of these products. At the same time, the decrease in the value of the national currency leads to a more competitive export in the world market. With the increase in demand, the price of tradable domestic goods is affected by upward price pressure and affects the domestic prices that were raised due to the increase in import prices. An increase in the demand for domestic products also leads to a greater demand for labor and can potentially increase wages and thus prices (Laflèche, 1996).

Taylor (2000) has related the degree of ERPT to the inflationary conditions of the countries. To explain the relationship between the degree of ERPT and inflationary environments, Taylor states that with the increase in the reaction of prices to the rise in costs as a result of the increase in the exchange rate, countries with high inflation always have a higher degree of ERPT; Therefore, the degree of ERPT depends on the monetary and currency systems of the countries, and in countries with valid monetary system and lower inflation rate, the ERPT is relatively low. Based on Taylor's point of view, the relationship between monetary systems and ERPT is mainly dependent on inflationary environments. In fact, high inflation environments can lead to an increase in ERPT. When the countries are in a high inflation situation, the effect of the exchange rate changes on the price level increases, and in such a situation, the ERPT will be completely different from the low inflation conditions in these countries (Anvari, Moradi, & Arman, 2024). When a country always faces high inflation rates and is placed in high inflation environments, because inflation expectations are at a high level, the price of imported goods increases and causes the purchasing power of domestic consumers to decrease; Therefore, domestic sellers will have to reduce their profit margins. According to these cases, the effect of inflation conditions on the degree of ERPT will depend on the economic conditions and structure of the country and empirical findings will be judged in this field (Sadeghi, Totonchi, Abtahi, & Tabatabaienasab, 2024).

Also, the literature has various theoretical and experimental arguments regarding ERPT changes in different consumer groups. The theoretical literature in this field refers to two main points. One branch of the literature emphasizes the nominal stickiness of prices; while another, focuses on microeconomics, emphasizes the structure and characteristics of the market and sub-sectors of the economy, as well as the different weights of tradable and non-tradable inputs in different sub-sectors of the economy. On the other hand, some explanations have paid attention to this issue from the angle of industrial structure and the differences between economic sub-sectors from the point of view of industrial organization, and they focus on features such as market structure, specifically, in this approach, on the differences between sub-sectors, from the point of view of the degree of substitutability between domestic and foreign goods, the structure of competition in those sub-sectors (both foreign and domestic competition), barriers to

entering the market, the activity of the degree of import penetration in the market and the relative size of the market. In a branch of literature that refers to the difference in price stickiness in creating different degrees of reaction between exchange rate and price in economic sub-sectors, for example, the study of Kosti, Dedola, and Leduc (2005) can be mentioned, which The format of a stochastic dynamic general equilibrium model made it possible for different economic sub-sectors to have different degrees of price stickiness and hence their reactions to exchange rate changes are different. In the form of these models, the degree of reaction of prices in economic sub-sectors is determined endogenously in the model and it is a function of the share of costs of distribution of goods in the market, the degree of substitution between goods and other factors that affect the amount of profits of companies. In general, the different structure of the market, the difference in the degree of trade openness, the difference in the variety of products, the different share of imported inputs, and also the non-tradable inputs in production in different sectors of an economy cause the price reaction of consumer groups to changes in the exchange rate (Heydari & Rashidi, 2019).

Empirical research review

(Sadeghi, Totonchi, Abtahi, & Tabatabaienasab, 2024) analyzed ERPT with an emphasis on the inflationary environment and the behavior of the central bank in Iran. For this purpose, the researchers used the threshold model (STAR) and quarterly data during the period of 2000:3-2019:4. The results of this research showed that in a low exchange rate regime, an increase in the exchange rate causes a decrease, and in a high exchange rate regime, it causes an increase in the price index. Also, there is a causal relationship between the exchange rate and inflation; That is, by increasing the exchange rate, inflation is created and lead to increase in the exchange rate again. Also, the researchers showed that the Central Bank's interventions in Iran were mostly aimed at controlling the growth of the exchange rate and prices. (Anvari, Moradi, & Arman, 2024) analyzed the effect of monetary regimes on the degree of ERPT in Iran from 1986 to 2017. For this purpose, researchers first extracted money supply regimes using the Markov-switching model. In this study, based on the results of the model, the money supply behavior is divided into two regimes, the first regime is the positive money supply regime and the second regime is the negative money supply regime. Then, by defining two dummy variables for each of the monetary regimes, the intersection effect of these variables along with variables such as the degree of trade openness, oil price, and positive and negative shocks of the exchange rate using NARDL method on the consumer price index has been investigated in the short and long term. The results of this research show that the degree of ERPT in the short and long term is incomplete and asymmetric. Also, positive and negative monetary regimes in the short and long term have asymmetric effects on the degree of ERPT in Iran. According to the results of the researchers, positive monetary regimes in the short and long term have positive and significant effects on the degree of ERPT to the consumer price index; While negative monetary regimes in the short term have a negative and significant effect with a lag, and in the long term they also have a negative and significant effect on the degree of ERPT to the consumer price index. (Anderl & Caporale, 2023) conducted a study on the non-linearity of ERPT to consumer prices and imports from January 1993 to August 2021. They used a smooth transition regression model to analyze different regimes of inflation expectations in five countries (UK, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, and Sweden). The study's findings indicated that

stabilizing inflation expectations contributes to a reduction in ERPT. (Kwon & Shin, 2023) investigates the nonlinearity effects of exchange rate shocks on inflation in South Korea using a vector autoregressive smooth transition model along with survey expectations data. The researchers found that the impact of exchange rate shocks is statistically greater in the low credit regime, especially in the short run. (Carrière-Swallow, Firat, Furceri, & Jiménez, 2023) estimated how the ERPT varies in different economies. Drawing on the experience of a large sample of advanced and emerging market economies over the past 30 years, the authors document that exchange rate pass-through is significantly greater in periods of high inflation and high uncertainty. Using a novel identification strategy, they also show that transmission is higher when exchange rate volatility is driven by US monetary policy. (Sa'ad, Usman, Omaye, & Yau, 2023) investigated the asymmetric effect of oil price and exchange rate on inflation in Nigeria during the period from 1970 to 2020 using the NARDL model. The researchers showed the existence of asymmetry among the research variables, which indicates that there is a non-linear interaction between the variables used in the research. The results of long-term estimates of researchers show that increasing (positive) oil price shocks have a greater impact on inflation than decreasing (negative) oil price shocks. In addition, it is evident from this result that the decrease in the exchange rate compared to the increase in the exchange rate in Nigeria has a significant effect on inflation. (Bilgili, Ünlü, Gençoğlu, & Kuşkaya, 2022) investigated the effect of ERPT in Turkey using quarterly data for the period 1998Q1:2019Q2. This paper runs several nonlinear models in which the determinants of domestic prices in Turkey. Researchers use the variables of consumer price index (CPI), dollar price, gross domestic product (GDP), industrial production index (IP), economic uncertainty and geopolitical risk index. The results of this research showed that the exchange rate and GDP follow a positive non-linear relationship with CPI in both regimes. IP has negative effect on CPI in the zero regime. Economic uncertainty positively affects CPI in Regime 1, while geopolitical risk is negatively related to CPI in Regime Zero. (Edwards & Cabezas, 2022) use data from Iceland to examine two often neglected aspects of the ERPT. First, they check whether the ERPT is different from the degree of international trade of goods. Second, they analyze whether the ERPT depends on the monetary policy framework. The result of researcher shows when Iceland revised its flexible inflation targeting, ERPT decreased, and the coefficients were significantly higher for tradable than for non-tradable. (Iliyasu & Sanusi, 2022) examine the role of announced exchange rate policy on ERPT in Nigeria using a structural VAR model. This study shows that when exchange rate interventions policy was anticipated through an announcement, ERPT was reduced by 12.81 percent. Researchers' estimates also show that exchange rate transmission in Nigeria is incomplete, moderate and slow. (Cheikh & Zaiid, 2020) examine ERPT for 10 European Union Member States (NMS) in the period 1996-2015. The researchers propose a non-linear panel smooth transition regression (PSTR) approach to estimation. The results of this research show that the inflation regime is the main macroeconomic driver of the ERPT. When inflation levels cross the threshold, i.e. in a high inflation environment, the degree of ERPT is higher. However, with a shift to a stable, low-inflation regime, for example, when inflation levels are below a threshold, ERPT decreases significantly in the NMS group. (Heydari & Rashidi, 2019) estimated the impact of exchange rate changes on the components of the producer price index (including industry, agriculture, and service sectors) using the structural vector autoregression (SVAR) model. For this purpose, the researchers used the quarterly data of the period 1991-2017 in Iran. The results of this research showed that in the agriculture

and services sector, ERPT has occurred incompletely (less than 100 percent); so that for a 100% increase in the exchange rate, the price in the service sector has increased by 40% and in the agricultural sector by 46%. In the industrial sector, unlike other economic sectors, ERPT has been almost complete and about 100%, so that in the 24th quarter, for a 100% increase in the exchange rate, producer prices in the industrial sector have increased by more than 97%. Also, the consumer price index has increased by 23% for a 100% increase in the exchange rate. (Tamizi, 2016) estimated the effect of economic openness and inflation rate on the intensity of ERPT in Iran during the years 1971 to 2010 using the ARDL method. The results of this research showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between the exchange rate and the export price index, and the degree of ERPT in Iran is equal to 0.83. (Lashkary, Abolhasani, Asgharpur, & Tamizi, 2015) using the GMM approach evaluate the ERPT in Iran and its most important trading partners during the years 2000 to 2010. The results of this research showed that the ERPT in Iran is incomplete and close to one.

Methodology

In this study, the quarterly data of the consumer price index and its 12 main groups, market exchange rate, openness index, government expenditures, oil revenues and gross domestic product at constant prices of 2015 during the period of 2000q2-2023q1 were used in the Iranian economy. All the required data were extracted from the website of the Central Bank of Iran. The current research model is a threshold regression model.

Ignoring the changing macroeconomic environment can lead to biased ERPT estimates. Although some existing empirical studies have suggested the role of macroeconomic factors on ERPT, they do not consider the existence of non-linear behavior or regime change in the ERPT mechanism (Cheikh & Zaied, 2020). Considering the importance of considering macroeconomic conditions and non-linear effects, and as well as citing the empirical studies of researchers such as (Sadeghi, Totonchi, Abtahi, & Tabatabaianasab, 2024), (Anderl & Caporale, 2023) and (Cheikh & Zaied, 2020) in this study, the threshold regression model was used to estimate ERPT in different inflation environments. We start with a standard multiple linear regression model with T observations and m potential thresholds (production regimes). For the observations in regime $j=1, 2, \dots, m$ we have the linear regression specification:

$$P_t = X_t'\beta + Z_t'\rho_j + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

The important point in relation (1) is that the regressors are divided into two groups. X are variables whose parameters do not change during different regimes; while Z are variables that have coefficients specific to each regime. In this research, based on different estimates for variable lags and also considering each variable as a regime-specific variable and calculating the sum of the squared errors of each estimate step by step, two intervals (first and fourth lag) have been considered for the variables. Furthermore, exchange rate variables (E) and government expenditures (G) are regime-specific variables and other variables are not dependent on the regime. According to (Bai & Perron, 1998) test, a threshold limit and two regimes have been determined. The research model is specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(P_t) = & B_0 + \beta_1 \ln(O_t) + \beta_2 \ln(O_{t-1}) + \beta_3 \ln(O_{t-4}) + \beta_4 \ln(Y_t) + \beta_5 \ln(Y_{t-1}) \\ & + \beta_6 \ln(Y_{t-4}) + \beta_7 \ln(Oi_t) + \beta_8 \ln(Oi_{t-1}) + \beta_9 \ln(Oi_{t-4}) \\ & + \{\theta_1 [\gamma_1 \ln(E_t) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \gamma_2 \ln(E_{t-1}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) \\ & + \gamma_3 \ln(E_{t-2}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \gamma_4 \ln(G_t) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) \\ & + \gamma_5 \ln(G_{t-1}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \gamma_6 \ln(G_{t-2}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t})] \\ & + \theta_2 [\delta_1 \ln(E_t) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \delta_2 \ln(E_{t-1}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) \\ & + \delta_3 \ln(E_{t-2}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \delta_4 \ln(G_t) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) \\ & + \delta_5 \ln(G_{t-1}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \delta_6 \ln(G_{t-2}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t})] \} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The $\theta_i, i = 1,2$ parameter determines which regime holds. If $i=1$, we are in the first regime, in which the value of $\theta_1 = 1$ and the value of $\theta_2 = 0$. Also, in the second regime $i=2$, the value of $\theta_1 = 0$ and $\theta_2 = 1$. As a result, the research model for the first and second regimes is specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(P_t) = & B_0 + \beta_1 \ln(O_t) + \beta_2 \ln(O_{t-1}) + \beta_3 \ln(O_{t-4}) + \beta_4 \ln(Y_t) + \beta_5 \ln(Y_{t-1}) \\ & + \beta_6 \ln(Y_{t-4}) + \beta_7 \ln(Oi_t) + \beta_8 \ln(Oi_{t-1}) + \beta_9 \ln(Oi_{t-4}) \\ & + \gamma_1 \ln(E_t) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \gamma_2 \ln(E_{t-1}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) \\ & + \gamma_3 \ln(E_{t-2}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \gamma_4 \ln(G_t) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) \\ & + \gamma_5 \ln(G_{t-1}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \gamma_6 \ln(G_{t-2}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \varepsilon_t \quad \text{Regim 1} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(P_t) = & B_0 + \beta_1 \ln(O_t) + \beta_2 \ln(O_{t-1}) + \beta_3 \ln(O_{t-4}) + \beta_4 \ln(Y_t) + \beta_5 \ln(Y_{t-1}) + \\ & \beta_6 \ln(Y_{t-4}) + \beta_7 \ln(Oi_t) + \beta_8 \ln(Oi_{t-1}) + \beta_9 \ln(Oi_{t-4}) + \delta_1 \ln(E_t) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \\ & \delta_2 \ln(E_{t-1}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \delta_3 \ln(E_{t-2}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \delta_4 \ln(G_t) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \\ & \text{Regim 2} \delta_5 \ln(G_{t-1}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \delta_6 \ln(G_{t-2}) \cdot g(\text{Inf}_{\text{EXP}_t}) + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In this study, the threshold variable is inflation expectations, which is measured by the level of the inflation rate in the previous quarter, which is based on different estimates of the threshold value equal to 15.1%. The variables of the research models are introduced in Table 1.

Table 1. Introduction of research variables

Symbol	Operational definition
P	Price index of consumer goods and services.
O	The ratio of total exports and imports to GDP.
Y	Gross domestic product at constant prices of 2015.
OI	The amount of Iran's total oil revenues.
E	Quarterly average price of the dollar in terms of Rials in the market
G	Total central government expenditure.
Inf _{EXP}	Inflation expectations (The inflation rate in the previous quarter).

It should be noted that in this research, the dependent variable is based on the international classification of COICOP (including 12 groups) and also the consumer price index (CPI) consists of 13 different groups, which include the following:

- CPI
- Food & non-alcoholic beverages
- Tobacco and narcotics
- Clothing & footwear
- Housing, water, electricity, gas and other fuels
- Furnishings, household equipment & routine household maintenance
- Health
- Transport
- Communication
- Recreation & culture
- Education
- Restaurants & hotels
- Miscellaneous goods & services

Findings

In this study, the Phillips-Perron test was used to check the stationarity of variables. The results of this test are reported in Table 2. According to Table 2, the level values of all variables are non-stationary; however, with the first-order differentiation, all variables become stationary, and as a result, they are integrated from the first order (I (1)). Considering that the variables used in the research model are I (1), before estimating the models, it is necessary to ensure the long-term relationship between the variables. For this purpose, was used Engel-Granger cointegration test. The results of this test are reported in Table 3. As can be seen in Table 3, based on the values of both tau and Z statistics, all estimated relationships are cointegrated and as a result, there is a long-term relationship between the variables.

Table 2. The results of the stationary test (Phillips-Perron test)

Variables	Test statistics		Test critical values	Result
	Level	First difference		
CPI	1.07	-4.49	-3.46	I(1)
Food & ...	0.04	-6.55	-3.46	I(1)
Tobacco & ...	-2.16	-6.12	-3.46	I(1)
Clothing & ...	-0.39	-3.90	-3.46	I(1)
Housing, ...	1.59	-4.67	-3.46	I(1)
Furnishings, ...	-0.74	-4.57	-3.46	I(1)
Health	-0.17	-7.07	-3.46	I(1)
Transport	0.14	-5.55	-3.46	I(1)
Communication	0.83	-5.00	-3.46	I(1)
Recreation & ...	-0.58	-5.62	-3.46	I(1)
Education	0.03	-11.39	-3.46	I(1)
Restaurants & ...	1.63	-4.48	-3.46	I(1)
Miscellaneous & ...	-0.40	-5.11	-3.46	I(1)
O	-3.31	-25.31	-3.46	I(1)
Y	-1.50	-7.40	-3.46	I(1)
OI	-2.33	-22.86	-3.46	I(1)
E	-1.05	-6.12	-3.46	I(1)
G	-1.10	-52.90	-3.46	I(1)

Table 3. The results of Cointegration test (Engel-Granger test)

Variables	tau-statistic	Prob.	z-statistic	Prob.
CPI	-7.45	0.00	-68.44	0.00
Food &	-7.04	0.00	-63.90	0.00
Tobacco &	-6.34	0.00	-54.96	0.00
Clothing &	-5.28	0.02	-78.51	0.00
Housing,	-7.26	0.00	-66.62	0.00
Furnishings,	-5.46	0.01	-44.71	0.01
Health	-7.23	0.00	-66.92	0.00
Transport	-7.54	0.00	-70.31	0.00
Communication	-6.36	0.00	-55.10	0.00
Recreation &	-4.93	0.04	-68.97	0.00
Education	-5.68	0.00	-49.86	0.00
Restaurants &	-7.70	0.00	-71.03	0.00
Miscellaneous &	-6.36	0.00	-55.1	0.00

The results of the linear part of the threshold regression model are presented in Table 4. According to Table 4, the variables OPEN, OI, Y and the first and fourth lags of these variables have a linear effect on consumer price indices.

As can be seen in Table 4, at the 95% confidence level of the index of openness in the current period, O, the first its lag, O (-1) and the fourth its lag, O (-4) on the CPI and

11 main sectors have a negative and significant effect (all groups except Communication). However, the openness and its first and fourth its lag have a positive and significant effect on the "Communication" group price index.

At the 95% confidence level, the variable of gross domestic product in the current period, Y has a negative and significant effect on the price index in the groups "Tobacco & narcotics", "Health", "Education" and "Miscellaneous goods & services" and in the groups "Communication" and "Transport" its effect on the price index is positive and significant; Also, the Y variable did not have a significant effect on other groups of consumer price indices.

At the 95% confidence level, the first lag of the gross domestic product, Y (-1) and its fourth lag, Y (-4) has a positive and significant effect on the price index of most groups (except communications) and the consumer price index; However, at the confidence level of 95%, the Y (-1) had a negative and significant effect on the price index of the "Communication" and did not have a significant effect on the price index of the "Housing, water, electricity, gas and other fuels" groups. Also, Y (-4) had a negative and significant effect on the "Communication" group, and it did not have a significant effect on the "Transport", "Recreation & culture" and "Restaurants & hotel" groups.

Table 4. Estimation results of the research threshold model (linear part)

COICOP	O	O (-1)	O (-4)	Y	Y (-1)	Y (-4)	OI	OI (-1)	OI (-4)
CPI	-0.25**	-0.27**	-0.34**	0.02	0.56**	0.30**	0.03	0.02	0.01
Food &	-0.30**	-0.29**	-0.42**	-0.07	0.53**	0.49**	0.04**	0.02	0.01
Tobacco &	-0.24**	-0.29**	-0.36**	-0.68**	0.75**	1.12**	0.02**	0.02**	0.03**
Clothing &	-0.24**	-0.24**	-0.34**	-0.21	0.50**	0.41**	0.04**	0.04**	0.02**
Housing,	-0.26**	-0.28**	-0.31**	0.03	0.69	0.24**	0.03**	0.02	0.01
Furnishings,	-0.14**	-0.21**	-0.27**	-0.14	0.54**	0.47**	0.02**	0.005	-0.00
Health	-0.38**	-0.29**	-0.37**	-0.32**	0.74**	0.80**	0.03**	0.03	0.04**
Transport	-0.10**	-0.26**	-0.31**	0.59**	0.34**	-0.37	0.01	0.00	-0.01
Communication	0.10**	0.09**	0.17**	0.57**	-0.16**	-0.65**	-0.01**	-0.02**	-0.01**
Recreation &	-0.12**	-0.09**	-0.14**	0.03	0.19**	0.01	0.01**	0.02**	0.01
Education	-0.29**	-0.22**	-0.19**	-0.28**	0.89**	0.37**	0.01	0.01	0.01
Restaurants &	-0.28**	-0.26**	-0.40**	0.00	0.57**	0.38	0.05**	0.04**	0.03
Miscellaneous &	-0.28**	-0.26**	-0.30**	-0.31**	0.63**	0.74**	0.02**	0.01**	0.02**

At the 95% confidence level, the variable of oil revenues in the current period, OI has had a positive and significant effect on the consumer price index in most of the groups defined in Table 4. However, the effect of this variable on the price index in the "Communication" group was negative and significant, and it did not have a significant effect in the "Transport", "Education" groups and the consumer price index.

At the 95% confidence level, the first lag of the oil income variable, OI (-1) on the price index in the groups "Tobacco & narcotics", "Clothing & footwear", "Recreation & culture", "Restaurants & hotels" and "Miscellaneous goods & services" had a positive and significant effect and in the "Communication" group it had a negative and significant

effect; Also, the variable OI (-1) did not have a significant effect on other groups of price indices.

At the 95% confidence level, the fourth lag of the oil income variable, OI (-4) has a significant and positive effect on the price index in the groups "Tobacco & narcotics", "Clothing & footwear", "Recreation & culture" and "Miscellaneous goods & services" and has had a negative and significant effect in the "Communication" group; Also, the OI (-4) did not have a significant effect on other groups of price indices.

Table 5.A. Estimation results of the research threshold model (non-linear part 1)

COICOP	Inf_EXP <15.1%						
	C	E	E (-1)	E (-4)	G	G (-1)	G (-4)
CPI	-6.67**	0.04	0.64**	-0.15**	0.08**	0.16**	0.06
Food &	-7.32**	0.01	0.99**	-0.39**	0.07**	0.18**	0.06
Tobacco &	-7.86**	0.42**	0.75**	-0.65**	0.09**	0.10**	-0.04**
Clothing &	-5.91**	-0.10**	0.80**	0.09	0.05**	0.08**	-0.01
Housing,	-6.31**	0.06	0.38**	-0.19**	0.10**	0.18**	0.09**
Furnishings,	-7.29**	0.03	0.68**	0.02	0.04**	0.11**	0.05**
Health	-9.19**	-0.06	0.78**	-0.09	0.14**	0.17**	-0.01
Transport	-5.08**	0.18**	0.47**	0.05	0.04**	0.11**	0.08**
Communication	1.11**	0.02	0.39**	-0.13	0.01	0.03	0.09
Recreation &	-3.48**	0.27**	0.48**	0.14	0.02	0.02	0.00
Education	-6.73**	0.05	0.51**	-0.37**	0.15**	0.19**	0.10**
Restaurants &	-7.50**	-0.08	0.73**	-0.06	0.09**	0.18**	0.02
Miscellaneous &	-8.50**	0.07	0.71**	-0.05	0.09**	0.14**	0.02

The results of the nonlinear component of the threshold regression model are displayed in Table 5.A & 5.B. According to Table 5.A & 5.B, the variables E and G, as well as the first and fourth lags of these variables, exhibit a nonlinear impact on price indices. As can be seen in Table 5.A & 5.B, the exchange rate variable in the current period, E has heterogeneous effects among different groups of the consumer price index during the inflation regimes. In the regime of low inflation expectations (expected inflation rate less than 15.1%) at the 95% confidence level, the effect of the E on the price index in the groups "Tobacco & narcotics", "Transport" and "Recreation & culture" has been positive and significant.; While in this inflationary regime, the effect of the E variable on the price index in the "Clothing & footwear" group is estimated to be negative and significant. Also, at the 95% confidence level, the effect of the E on the price index in other consumer price index groups is not statistically significant; Meanwhile, in the regime of high inflation expectations (expected inflation rate greater than or equal to 15.1 percent), the E had a positive and significant effect on the price index of "Transport", "Communication" and "Recreation & culture" groups. Also, in this inflationary regime, the E has had a negative and significant effect on the price index of other investigated groups as well as the CPI.

The first lag of the exchange rate, E (-1) has heterogeneous effects among the groups of the consumer price index in the two inflationary regimes. In the regime of low inflation expectations (expected inflation rate less than 15.1 percent), at the 95 percent confidence level, the effect of the E(-1) on the price index in all groups as well as the CPI has been positive and significant; While in the regime of high inflation expectations, the effect of the E(-1) on the "Communication" group is not statistically significant, and in other investigated groups, the effect of this variable is positive and significant.

The fourth lag of exchange rate, E (-4) has heterogeneous effects among different groups of price index in two inflationary regimes. In the regime of low inflation expectations (expected inflation rate less than 15.1%) at the 95% confidence level, the E (-4) on the price index of the groups "Food & non-alcoholic beverages", "Tobacco & narcotics", "Housing, water, "electricity, gas and other fuels" and the CPI have a negative and significant effect, and in other consumption groups, the effect of this variable is not statistically significant; While in the regime of high inflation expectations, the effect of E (-4) is not statistically significant only on the "Communication" group, and in other consumption groups, the effect of this variable is positive and significant.

Table 5.B. Estimation results of the research threshold model (non-linear part 2)

COICOP	Inf_EXP=>15.1%						
	C	E	E (-1)	E (-4)	G	G (-1)	G (-4)
CPI	-7.08**	-0.15**	0.45**	0.21**	0.09**	0.16**	0.15**
Food &	-7.88**	-0.15**	0.58**	0.19**	0.08	0.18**	0.16**
Tobacco &	-8.38**	-0.13**	0.74**	0.10**	-0.04	0.03**	0.13**
Clothing &	-6.14**	-0.11**	0.47**	0.35**	0.02	0.08**	0.13**
Housing,	-6.82**	-0.22**	0.26**	0.19**	0.13**	0.18**	0.18**
Furnishings,	-7.70**	-0.16**	0.63**	0.24**	0.07**	0.11**	0.14**
Health	-8.98**	-0.32**	0.58**	0.27**	0.01	0.12**	0.22**
Transport	-5.58**	0.09**	0.38**	0.22**	0.18**	0.15**	0.04**
Communication	1.05**	0.30**	-0.02	-0.01	0.07**	0.09**	-0.02
Recreation &	-3.46**	0.21**	0.36**	0.29**	-0.02	0.02	0.09**
Education	-6.81**	-0.18**	0.34**	0.06**	0.07**	0.15**	0.30**
Restaurants &	-7.94**	-0.14**	0.41**	0.33**	0.03	0.2**	0.18**
Miscellaneous &	-8.60**	-0.16**	0.63**	0.21**	0.06**	0.12**	0.14**

The government expenditure, G and its lags in two regimes of inflationary expectations have heterogeneous effects on the price index in different groups. In the regime of low inflation expectations (expected inflation rate less than 15.1%), variable G and its first lag at the 95% confidence level in most consumer groups (except "Recreation & culture" and "Communication") have a positive and significant effect on the price index. Also, at the 95% confidence level of the fourth lag of variable G in the low inflation regime, there is a positive and significant effect in the consumption groups "Housing, water, electricity, gas and other fuels", "Furnishings, household equipment & routine household

maintenance", "Transport" and "Education" and had a negative and significant effect on the "Tobacco & narcotics" group.

Based on the evidence in Table 5.A & 5.B, in the regime of high inflationary expectations, variable G at the 95% confidence level in most consumption groups (except "Food & non-alcoholic beverages", "Tobacco & narcotics", "Clothing & footwear", "Health", "Recreation & culture" and "Restaurants & hotel") had a positive and significant effect on the price index. Also, at the 95% confidence level, the first lag of G in the high inflation regime has had a positive and significant effect on the price index in all groups (except "Recreation & culture"). At the 95% confidence level, the fourth lag of G in the high inflation regime has had a positive and significant effect on the price index of that group in all groups (except "Communication").

Table 6. ERPT according to COICOP groups in two inflationary regimes

COICOP	Low inflation regime	High inflation regime
CPI	0.483	0.502
Food &	0.597	0.617
Tobacco &	0.521	0.707
Clothing &	0.701	0.712
Housing,	0.183	0.230
Furnishings,	0.683	0.703
Health	0.783	0.525
Transport	0.658	0.657
Communication	0.389	0.304
Recreation &	0.751	0.851
Education	0.138	0.217
Restaurants &	0.731	0.600
Miscellaneous goods &	0.706	0.676

To calculate the overall effect of ERPT in each regime, the effects of the E variable and its statistically significant lags are summed together.

As can be seen in Table 6 and Figures 2 and 3 in general, the ERPT to the total consumer price index, CPI is larger in the high inflation regime than in the low inflation regime; however, significant differences can be seen between the two inflation regimes in the 12 groups. In the low inflation regime, the degree of ERPT varies between 0.138 and 0.783, and in the "Communication", "Housing, water, electricity, gas and other fuels" and "Education" groups, the degree of ERPT compared to CPI is lower and in other COICOP groups is higher than CPI. Also, in this inflationary regime, the highest degree of ERPT is assigned to the "Health" group and the lowest amount to the "Education" group.

Figure 2. Comparison of ERPT in the low inflation regime

Figure 3. Comparison of ERPT in the high inflation regime

In the high inflation regime, the degree of ERPT to consumer price indices varies between 0.217 and 0.854, and similar to the low inflation regime in the groups "Communication", "Housing, water, electricity, gas and other fuels" and "Education" The currency is lower than the total consumer price index, and in other COICOP groups, the transfer degree is higher than the CPI. Also, in this inflationary regime, the highest exchange rate pass-through is allocated to the "Recreation & culture" group and the lowest amount to the "Education" group.

Evaluation of the robustness of the results

In this section, to ensure the stability and robustness of the results, the value of ERPT is estimated by considering the threshold values of 10% and 30% for the expected inflation rate in two inflation regimes.

Based on the evidence presented in Table 7, by changing the threshold value of inflation expectations to 10% and 30%, the overall results of the research did not change much. Considering the threshold limit of 10% for inflation expectations, the value of ERPT for CPI and its 8 subgroups is greater in values of expected inflation above 10% than expected inflation below 10%. Also, considering the threshold limit of 30% for inflation expectations, the value of ERPT for CPI and its 9 subgroups in high expected inflation values of 30% is greater than expected inflation values of less than 30%; Therefore, it can be argued that the research results have not changed much by changing the threshold value of inflation expectations.

Table 7. ERPT sensitivity results to changing threshold value

COICOP	expected inflation			
	> 10%	< 10%	> 30%	< 30%
CPI	0.552	0.650	0.431	0.579
Food &	0.678	0.731	0.561	0.671
Tobacco &	0.620	0.737	0.711	0.464
Clothing &	0.755	1.014	0.536	0.825
Housing,	0.290	0.402	0.431	0.518
Furnishings,	0.757	0.793	0.587	0.794
Health	0.892	0.540	0.668	0.634
Transport	0.799	0.697	0.758	0.685
Communication	0.139	0.263	0.271	0.323
Recreation &	0.863	0.865	0.885	0.939
Education	0.245	0.303	0.210	0.283
Restaurants &	0.779	0.647	0.664	0.565
Miscellaneous goods &	0.873	0.709	0.657	0.771

Conclusion and discussion, and recommendations

The analysis of the exchange rate pass-through is very effective on the path of macro policies of a country. Knowing about the ERPT and its reaction to different inflation environments helps economic policymakers to adopt appropriate exchange policies. Iran's economy is highly dependent on foreign exchange earnings from oil exports, and changes and fluctuations in the exchange rate can affect the Iranian economy through the import of consumer, intermediate and capital goods. In this study, the effects of ERPT under inflationary regimes on the consumer price index and its main groups are estimated using quarterly data of 2000q2-2023q1 in Iran. The main findings of this research can be summarized as follows:

First, there is strong evidence of non-linearity and regime-dependence of ERPT in different groups of consumer price index; So that considering different thresholds, there are many differences in ERPT in COICOP groups in Iran. This research finding is consistent with the results of many studies including (Anvari, Moradi, & Arman, 2024), Anderl & Caporale, (2023) & (Sadeghi, Totonchi, Abtahi, & Tabatabaianasab, 2024). The non-linearity of the ERPT can be caused by various factors in Iran's economy, including price stickiness (mainly downward), government interventions in determining prices,

granting subsidies and preferential exchange rates to goods in inflationary conditions or the state of the business cycle.

Second, there is evidence of the effect of intensifying inflationary expectations on the increase of ERPT. In general, when consumers have high inflation expectations, the prices of most commodity groups respond more strongly to exchange rate changes, which indicates that managing inflation expectations in Iran's economy can reduce ERPT. In monetary systems that emphasize the stability and targeting of inflation, the expectation is that the degree of ERPT or the correlation between exchange rate changes and inflation be lower; Because in the monetary system of inflation targeting, which is accompanied by the control of inflationary deviations, the shocks to the economic policy are small, Therefore, it can be expected that in the conditions of low inflation expectations, the effects of exchange rate changes on the prices of domestic goods and services will be relatively less. These findings are consistent with the results by (Sadat Hoseyni, Asgharpur, & Haghighat, 2018), Anderl & Caporale, (2023) & (Sadeghi, Totonchi, Abtahi, & Tabatabaieenasab, 2024); so, they also estimated the effects of the inflation regime on the ERPT.

Thirdly, there is a significant difference between consumer groups in ERPT in two inflation regimes (low and high inflation expectations); So, It is not possible to have a one-size-fits-all approach for all sectors. It is recommended to formulate government support policies based on the impact of the exchange rate on each sector's inflation and considering their share in consumer spending during both low and high inflation periods. These policies should aim to have maximum control over the inflation rate with minimal market intervention. Specifically, to further control inflation during low inflation expectation periods, the government should focus on supporting the health, recreation, and culture sectors. Additionally, the government should provide more support to the entertainment, culture, and textile sectors in times of intensifying inflationary expectations.

Also, the results show that the ERPT in Iran is not complete, which was found in various studies such as (Tamizi, 2016) and (Lashkary, Abolhasani, Asgharpur, & Tamizi, 2015) is also confirmed. The imperfection of ERPT is because the price of consumer goods is not only dependent on the exchange rate but also other factors have been effective in the fluctuation of these prices. For example, labor wages in Iran are determined based on bargaining between the government, employers, and workers, and especially in recent years, they have not grown in proportion to the changes in the exchange rate or inflation rate.

In general, it can be argued, the increase in the ERPT is dependent on the conditions of inflationary expectations, therefore, in Iran, a triangle is formed between the exchange rate, inflation and speculative activities, in such a way that in the pyramid of this triangle exchange rate is the influencing channel of inflation and speculation in Iran's economy. With the increase in the inflation rate in the Iranian economy, the value of the national currency decreases compared to foreign currencies, which itself leads to an increase in the intensity of inflation and its stability, and also stimulates speculation activities; therefore, the main factor of ERPT increase in Iran is inflation. As a result, the monetary policy maker must control the extreme fluctuations of the exchange rate in the first step,

because the main factor of increasing inflation and speculative activities and the so-called pyramid of this triangle is the exchange rate fluctuations. In the next step, the inflationary environment should be reduced. One of the proposed policies in this regard is controlling liquidity or directing liquidity towards productive activities related to increasing GDP. Therefore, pursuing policies that simultaneously target exchange rate fluctuations, inflation reduction and speculative activities can help Iran's economic stability. The country's macroeconomic and monetary policymakers should be aware that changes in the exchange rate in each period have a different effect on inflation. The extent of this effect is influenced by various conditions and factors, especially inflation expectations. According to the results of the present study during the studied period, the ERPT has changed from a minimum of 13.8% to a maximum of 85.1% in each quarter, so if the goal of the economic policy maker and the central bank is to control and stabilize inflation, the exchange rate should also stabilize and avoid drastic changes of it.

Food and health expenses are classified as essential household needs. Considering that the ERPT in both inflation regimes for these two groups of expenses is greater than 0.5; It can be argued that more than half of the inflation of food and healthcare groups in Iran is affected by exchange rate changes; Therefore, it is suggested that the government pay attention to this issue in formulating foreign exchange policies. To stay in line with the well-being and livelihood of low-income households in Iran, it is necessary to formulate preferential currency policies in such a way that households can properly provide their essential needs. As a result, it can be said that if the currency policy of basic goods is carried out accurately and purposefully, the welfare of Iranian households can be improved in the conditions of currency shocks.

Abbreviations

<i>ERPT</i>	Exchange rate Pass-through
<i>TAR</i>	Threshold Regression model
β_i (1,2,3 ... k)	Regression coefficients
COICOP	The Classification of Individual Consumption According to Purpose
GDP	Gross Domestic Product

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